

Working paper – Deliverable 6.2

Increasing employment opportunities for individuals in vulnerable positions – the impact of employment policies during changing economic conditions

A comparative analysis of COVID-19
labour market policies targeting
migrants

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PATHS2INCLUDE

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**European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations**

Title: Increasing employment opportunities for individuals in vulnerable positions – the impact of employment policies during changing economic conditions

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Definitions	
Migrants	Individuals who reside in a country other than their country of birth, regardless of their legal status or reason for migration.
Nationality	Legal citizenship status granted by a state, determining an individual's formal membership and rights within that country.
Non-standard	Employment arrangements that deviate from the standard full-time, open-ended contract, such as part-time, temporary, agency, or self-employment without stable contracts
Non-formal	Work activities that are not covered by formal labour regulations, social security contributions, or official employment contracts; often occur in the informal economy.
Civil-law contracts (Poland)	Contracts for specific tasks (umowa o dzieło) or services (umowa zlecenie) regulated by civil law rather than labour law; they do not provide full labour protections or social insurance coverage.
Domestic work registry (Spain)	Official registration system for domestic workers employed in private households under Spain's <i>Special System for Household Employees</i> (Régimen Especial de Empleados del Hogar).
Employment rate (EU-LFS)	The employment rate is the percentage of persons under employment in relation to the comparable total population.
Employment (EU-LFS)	Employment covers persons living in private households, who during the reference week performed work, for at least 1 hour, for pay, profit or family gain, or were not at work but had a job or business from which they were temporarily absent, for example because of illness, holidays, maternal or paternal leave or training.
Actual working hours (EU-LFS)	Actual hours worked in the reference week are the hours the person spends in work activities during the reference week. They provide measurement of direct labour input. Working hours are collected in time intervals based on a half-hour scale (i.e. 0-0.5 hours, 0.5-1.0 hours, 1.0-1.5 hours, etc.). Specifically, average actual weekly hours are the number of hours actually worked per week in the main job, in the reference week, namely the hours spent in work activities including unpaid overtime. Periods of absence from work, such as sick leave, holidays and commuting time, account for 0 hours of work.
Usual working hours (EU-LFS)	Usual hours worked are the number of hours per week usually worked in the main job. They are the

	<p>modal value of the actual hours worked per week over a long reference period, excluding weeks when an absence from work occurs (e.g. holidays, leaves, strikes). They provide measurement of the organisation of working time. Working hours are collected in time intervals based on a half-hour scale (i.e. 0-0.5 hours, 0.5-1.0 hours, 1.0-1.5 hours, etc.). Specifically, average usual weekly hours are the number of hours usually worked per week in the main job that comprises all hours including extra hours, either paid or unpaid, which the person normally works. It excludes the travelling time between home and workplace, the time for the main meal break, education and non-job-related training. It includes production activities, ancillary activities (travel between different places of work, personnel management), education and training necessary for carrying out the work.</p>
Labour market slack (EU-LFS)	<p>A measure of unused or underutilized labour supply including unemployed, underemployed part-time workers, people seeking a job but not immediately available to work, and people available to work but not seeking it (as a share of the working-age population).</p>

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted labour markets worldwide, exacerbating existing inequalities and exposing structural vulnerabilities among already marginalised populations. Migrant workers were particularly affected due to their overrepresentation in precarious, low-paid, and informal employment (Fasani & Mazza, 2023; Borjas & Cassidy, 2021). Even before the pandemic, many faced unstable working conditions, limited access to social protections, and exclusion from collective bargaining structures (Eichhorst, Marx & Rinne, 2020). As the crisis unfolded, the sectors in which migrants are heavily concentrated, such as hospitality, domestic work, agriculture, and health care, were either severely disrupted by lockdowns or required continued in-person work under unsafe conditions (Guadagno, 2020). Migrant workers in essential roles faced disproportionate health risks due to inadequate workplace protections and often lacked access to paid sick leave or healthcare (ILO, 2021). At the same time, migrants with irregular legal status or working informally were frequently excluded from government support schemes, including job retention programmes and income support benefits (Eichhorst, 2022), deepening economic insecurity and hindering recovery prospects. Migrant women experienced a compounded vulnerability: they are over-represented in informal care and cleaning services (jobs with little protection and high exposure to the virus) while also assuming increased caregiving responsibilities at home due to school and childcare closures (Guadagno, 2020; ILO, 2021).

These outcomes reflected pre-existing disadvantages. Migrants, especially non-EU migrants, entered the pandemic more likely to hold temporary contracts, earn lower wages, and work in occupations with limited scope for remote work (Fasani & Mazza, 2020). Non-EU migrant workers were 48% more likely than natives to hold temporary contracts, and over half were concentrated in the bottom income deciles (Fasani & Mazza, 2020). Evidence from the EU Labour Force Survey indicates sharper employment declines for non-EU migrants compared to natives and EU-born migrants in 2020; by Q1 2021, employment rates had fallen by nearly 4.5 percentage points for the non-EU born versus about 2 percentage points for natives, and the probability of job termination for non-EU migrants was up to double that of natives across age groups, particularly among younger migrants and recent arrivals (Mazza et al., 2022). Sectoral concentration magnified these risks: 38% of cleaners and helpers and 19% of personal care workers were migrants (occupations with limited telework possibilities and high contact intensity) (Fasani & Mazza, 2020). Alongside economic factors, administrative and legal barriers (eligibility tied to formal employment or residency, language and information gaps, and fear of legal repercussions) further constrained access to protective measures (OECD, 2020; Fasani & Mazza, 2023; Mazza et al., 2022). Few policies addressed the intersectional vulnerabilities of migrant women, as caregiver-support measures such as flexible work arrangements or parental leave extensions typically applied only to formal employees (Guadagno, 2020). A lack of disaggregated data by country of birth or ethnicity in many contexts also hindered monitoring and the design of targeted interventions able to mitigate disproportionate risks in real time (Berchet et al., 2023).

In this context, this working paper examines how labour-market vulnerability evolved for migrant workers during the pandemic and evaluates the inclusiveness of policy responses in five European countries: Germany, Ireland, Norway, Poland and Spain. The analysis pursues two objectives: 1) to analyse the labour-market policies and measures implemented in response to the COVID-19 crisis in these five countries; and 2) to assess whether and how these measures addressed the specific challenges faced by migrant workers. The country selection captures distinct welfare-regime types and labour-market structures (Esping-Andersen, 1990; Deacon,

1993). The pandemic generated a profound and uneven shock across European labour markets: contact-intensive sectors such as accommodation and food services, arts, and entertainment experienced the largest contractions, and within sectors non-EU-born workers faced systematically higher job-loss risks (Eurostat, 2020–2021; Mazza et al., 2022). At EU level, the “Support to Mitigate Unemployment Risks in an Emergency” (SURE) instrument provided financial assistance to fund short-time work and similar job-retention schemes, helping maintain labour-market attachment for formally employed workers (European Commission, 2021). At the same time, comparative evidence highlights a divide between protections for standard employees via job-retention schemes and the often more limited or newer supports for the self-employed and atypical/non-standard workers (Eurofound, 2021). These contrasts across welfare regimes (e.g., contribution-linked access, reliance on temporary emergency payments, universalist designs) frame the cross-national variation examined here.

Methodologically, the paper combines quantitative and qualitative evidence in a comparative framework. Descriptive analyses based on the EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) (Eurofound, 2025) and the Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker (OxCGRT) (Hale et al., 2021) are first employed to set the background, outlining differences in labour market and migrant integration during the COVID-19 pandemic in the selected countries. Building on this contextual foundation, the paper then adopts a qualitative approach to evaluate policy design and inclusiveness, focusing on features that shape access for migrants: eligibility rules and residency or contribution requirements, treatment of non-standard forms of employment, sectoral and occupational focus, and the presence of language support or targeted information. The analysis aims to identify gaps in policy frameworks and to highlight practices that can support more inclusive labour-market strategies in future crises and recovery efforts. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the background of the study, comparing the labour market position of migrants and natives during the COVID-19 pandemic. Section 3 outlines the methods employed in the qualitative analysis of labour market-related policy responses. Section 4 summarises the main types of COVID-19 labour market policy responses. Section 5 presents the results, and Section 6 concludes.

2. Labour market contexts in the selected countries during the COVID-19 pandemic

The descriptive evidence from the EU-LFS and the OxCGRT databases highlights that the COVID-19 pandemic had an immediate and unequal impact on employment outcomes, with migrant workers consistently more exposed to labour market risks than natives.

Table 1 shows the timeline and intensity of workplace closures implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic across selected countries. In March 2020, measures of workplace closing were introduced in all countries. Ireland implemented an immediate and strict lockdown, moving directly to level 3, which required the closure of nearly all workplaces except essential services. Others, such as Germany, Norway or Spain adopted a more gradual approach, first introducing partial closures (level 2) before escalating to a full lockdown for a few months.

Table 1. Workplace closing during the COVID-19 pandemic

	Workplace closing																																							
	2020												2021												2022															
	jan	feb	mar	apr	may	jun	jul	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	mar	apr	may	jun	jul	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	mar	apr	may	jun	jul	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec				
Germany	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Ireland	0	0	3	3	3	2	1	3	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Norway	0	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Poland	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Spain	0	0	2	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0

0 – No measures, 1 – Workplace closing recommended, 2 – workplace closing only for some sectors, 3 – workplace closing for all but essential workers.

Source: Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker; own elaboration.

As it can be seen in table 1, all countries maintained workplace restrictions to varying degrees until the first half of 2022. These measures, together with the broader social and economic disruptions caused by the pandemic, had significant consequences for labour markets, as previously discussed. In the following, we examine how this situation affected workers by comparing native- and foreign-born populations. Specifically, we focus on differences in employment rate, actual hours worked, usual hours worked, and labour market slack, providing a comprehensive picture of the unequal impact of the pandemic on these groups of workers in the selected countries.

Employment rate

Figure 1 displays trends in employment rates for migrants and natives from 2018 to 2022 across the five countries. In Spain, migrant employment rates dropped sharply in 2020, reflecting the strong impact of the pandemic, and they partially recovered in subsequent years, returning to pre-pandemic levels by 2022. In contrast, Germany and Norway experienced only moderate declines in 2020, followed by a relatively quick recovery, with migrant employment returning to or slightly exceeding 2019 levels. In Ireland, migrant employment rate was higher than native employment rate in 2019 with a decline in 2020 reaching the rate of native workers, and the rate increased markedly by 2022, surpassing that of natives. Poland shows a distinct pattern, with migrant employment rates consistently higher than those of natives, peaking in 2021 before a slight decline. Overall, these trends reveal substantial cross-country variation, with Spain showing a more persistent negative impact on migrant employment, while in Ireland and Poland migrants appear to have been less affected or even benefited from post-pandemic labour market dynamics.

Figure 1. Employment rate by migrant origin, 2018-2022

Source: EU-LFS microdata; own elaboration.

Note: Based on EU-LFS 2018-2022. Individuals aged 25-54.

Actual hours worked

Figure 2 shows the evolution of actual working hours for migrants and natives during the same period. In all contexts, there was a visible decline in hours worked in 2020, coinciding with the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by a gradual recovery in subsequent years. The reduction in actual working hours was particularly pronounced for migrants in Germany, Poland and Spain. In Germany and Ireland, the decrease was more moderate, with both migrants and natives following similar patterns, and by 2022 migrant working hours had nearly returned to pre-pandemic levels. Poland presents a slightly different trajectory, with migrants consistently working similar or slightly more hours than natives before the pandemic, but this trend reversed after the pandemic. These results indicate that while the pandemic temporarily reduced working hours across all groups, the extent of the disruption and the speed of recovery varied across countries, with migrants in some contexts, such as Poland, appearing more vulnerable to reductions in working time.

Figure 2. Actual hours worked by migrant origin, 2018-2022

Source: EU-LFS microdata; own elaboration.

Note: Based on EU-LFS 2018-2022. Individuals aged 25-54.

Usual hours worked

Figure 3 illustrates the trends in usual working hours. Compared to actual hours worked, the patterns show greater stability over time, with no big declines in 2020 during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic. In Germany and Norway, migrants consistently reported slightly fewer usual working hours than natives. In Spain and Ireland, differences between migrants and natives were minimal throughout the period, with parallel trends and limited disruption during the pandemic. Poland stands out for having consistently higher usual working hours for both

groups, with a slightly decline in usual hours for migrants in 2021 and 2022. Overall, these results suggest that while the pandemic led to temporary reductions in actual hours worked (as seen in the previous figure), migrants' usual working hours remained relatively stable, indicating that the crisis primarily affected the intensity of work rather than contractual or expected working hours.

Figure 3. Usual hours worked by migrant origin, 2018-2022

Source: EU-LFS microdata; own elaboration.

Note: Based on EU-LFS 2018-2022. Individuals aged 25-54.

Labour market slack

Figure 4 shows that migrants consistently exhibit higher levels of labour market slack¹ compared to natives, indicating greater underutilization of their labour supply. In Germany and Spain, the gap between the two groups widened significantly in 2020, as migrants experienced a sharper increase in slack. While levels decreased somewhat in subsequent years, they remained above pre-pandemic levels by 2022, particularly in Spain. Norway and Ireland also show a temporary rise in slack for migrants in 2020 and 2021, followed by a return to pre-pandemic levels in 2022. In Poland, slack remained relatively low and stable throughout the entire period, with only minor differences between migrants and natives. These patterns suggest that the pandemic had a disproportionately negative effect on migrants in several countries, especially Germany and Spain, where they faced higher risks of underemployment and labour market exclusion.

¹ a measure of unused or underutilized labour supply including unemployed, underemployed part-time workers, people seeking a job but not immediately available to work, and people available to work but not seeking it (as a share of the working-age population).

Figure 4. Labour market slack by migrant origin, 2018-2022

Source: EU-LFS microdata; own elaboration.

Note: Based on EU-LFS 2018-2022. Individuals aged 25-54.

Taken together, the descriptive results confirm that the pandemic not only generated a general labour market shock, but also exacerbated structural disadvantages faced by migrants. Across the five countries, migrants experienced sharper contractions in employment and working hours, as well as greater risks of underutilisation, compared to natives. Even where recovery trends were visible in 2021 and 2022, in some cases, these did not erase the widening of inequalities produced by the crisis.

3. Data and methods

The qualitative analysis of policies draws on Eurofound’s PolicyWatch database (2025), which compiles national policy measures related to employment, income support, and social protection introduced or adapted during and after the pandemic. To focus specifically on policies relevant to our aims, we applied a series of cleaning and selection criteria. First, we excluded any policies created or implemented outside the COVID-19 period, specifically those not introduced between 2020 and 2022. Second, we removed policies unrelated to the COVID-19 crisis, such as those introduced in response to other events like the war in Ukraine. Third, we excluded measures that were not connected to the labour market, for instance, policies focused exclusively on public health or poverty (see exclusion criteria in Appendix 2). Finally, we removed business-oriented policies that had no direct or no clear indirect impact on workers.

This screening reduced the sample from 501 to 105 measures and provides the basis for our comparative analysis:

Table 2. Selection of measures

	Initial Sample	Final sample
Germany	104	28
Ireland	87	20
Norway	76	18
Poland	98	16
Spain	136	23

For each selected measure, we retrieved and systematically reviewed the official documents, or when they were unavailable, we analysed any other available document from official sources (e.g., government press releases) explaining the measure. The initial extraction was assisted by ChatGPT version 5, guided by precise instructions on the concepts and fields to capture (Appendix 1). The research team then performed random checks against the originals to verify accuracy.

To capture effective access for migrant workers, each policy was coded for: (1) explicit targeting of migrants; (2) inclusion or exclusion of the informal economy (e.g., no contract, undeclared work, lack of social-security registration); (3) inclusion of workers in non-standard employment (part-time, fixed-term, temporary agency); (4) sectoral/occupational focus where migrants are overrepresented (e.g., care, agriculture, hospitality); (5) access modality (e.g., automatic vs. application-based); and (6) potential barriers such as language, documentation, and administrative complexity. We then combined thematic and comparative analysis to identify cross-national variation in whether migrants were addressed explicitly or implicitly, how eligibility and implementation mechanisms facilitated or restricted access, and the extent to which measures tackled known vulnerabilities.

ChatGPT

In this study, we employed artificial intelligence (AI) tools (ChatGPT version 5) to assist in the review of policy documents. The AI was used exclusively as a support tool within a highly controlled and transparent analytical process. Its role was limited to facilitating the review and synthesis of textual content from official policy documents that had been manually selected and extracted by the research team. In other words, ChatGPT did not perform any autonomous data collection or web searches. It was prompted to analyse only the content of documents explicitly provided by the researchers and guided by precise instructions on the concepts and fields to capture (Appendix 1).

Prior to AI-assisted review, the team carried out a detailed selection and pre-screening phase, ensuring that only relevant and reliable documents from official and verifiable sources were included. During the review, ChatGPT was instructed to base its interpretations strictly on the

content of these materials that were manually uploaded. Following the automated review, random manual checks were conducted to verify the consistency and accuracy of the AI-generated summaries and classifications. This multi-step control process was crucial to maintain methodological rigour and to prevent potential biases or overinterpretations by the AI.

See section *Use of artificial intelligence in document analysis* for further discussion on advantages and limitations.

4. Labour market policies implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic

This section analyses how Germany, Ireland, Norway, Poland and Spain responded to the labour market challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the protection of migrant workers. The analysis examines to what extent migrants are explicitly mentioned in labour market policies and measures or, alternatively, are included indirectly through measures targeting sectors or occupations where they are overrepresented, as well as specific types of employment in which they are concentrated, such as non-formal or non-standard work. It also considers the accessibility of these policies for migrants and the potential barriers they may face when trying to benefit from them. By combining quantitative indicators and qualitative evidence, we identify differences in the inclusivity of responses, highlighting the structural factors shaping labour market protections during the crisis.

When looking at the types of interventions, *job retention and income support* schemes were the key responses to the pandemic in all five countries. These schemes aimed to prevent mass layoffs by allowing employers to temporarily reduce working hours or suspend contracts while workers received income support. In Germany, the *Kurzarbeit* scheme was the central instrument, playing a decisive role in stabilizing employment allowing employers to reduce working hours while the state compensated workers for lost earnings. Spain adopted a similar mechanism through the *ERTEs* (Expedientes de Regulación Temporal de Empleo), which provided temporary layoff mechanisms with strong government support, particularly in sectors such as tourism and construction where migrants are overrepresented. Norway introduced temporary adjustments to unemployment benefits and layoff rules, effectively functioning as a job retention system. Poland's *Anti-crisis Shields* also included wage co-financing and the deferral of social security contributions to help companies retain workers. In Ireland, job retention was integrated within broader wage subsidy programs rather than implemented as a separate scheme.

Table 3 shows the timeline and intensity of income support measures implementation. All five countries began implementing income support measures starting in March 2020. From the start, all countries introduced income support covering more than 50% of lost wages, except for Poland, which initially provided support covering less than 50% of lost wages. In October 2020, Poland increased the level of support to above 50%. These measures remained in place until 2022, with Poland being the first country to phase them out in March 2022, followed by Ireland and Spain in July 2022, while Germany and Norway maintained them until the end of the year.

Table 3. Income support measures implemented during COVID-19 pandemic

	Income support																																															
	2020												2021												2022																							
	jan	feb	mar	apr	may	jun	jul	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	mar	apr	may	jun	jul	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	mar	apr	may	jun	jul	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec												
Germany	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2								
Ireland	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Norway	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0			
Poland	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Spain	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0

0 – no income support measures, 1 – income support <50% of lost salary, 2 – income support >50% of lost salary.

Source: Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker; own elaboration.

Wage subsidies, defined as direct financial transfers to employers to maintain payrolls regardless of working hours, were especially prevalent in Ireland, Norway, Spain, and Poland. Ireland’s Employment Wage Subsidy Scheme (EWSS) was one of the most comprehensive, providing broad-based support to businesses across multiple sectors and ensuring that workers remained formally employed. Norway’s Lønnsstøtteordning [Wage support scheme] encouraged firms to rehire or retain workers during reopening phases. Spain combined wage subsidies elements with job retention through direct support for self-employed workers and affected companies. Poland’s Shield 6.0 included partial wage subsidies for workers with civil-law contracts. Germany, by contrast, did not implement a separate wage subsidy scheme, relying instead on Kurzarbeit, which already included wage compensation for reduced hours. A summary of these measures can be seen in Table 4 that shows the main employment protection measures adopted during the COVID-19 pandemic across the five countries, distinguishing between three broad categories: job retention schemes, wage subsidies, and other employment measures aimed at self-employed or non-standard workers.

Table 4. Selected employment protection measures during the COVID-19 pandemic

Country	Job retention (short-time work / furlough)	Income support to workers (self-employed, non-standard...)	Wage subsidy (direct support)	Other employment, measures (self-employed, non-standard, training, etc.)
Germany	Kurzarbeit – reduced hours with state compensation	Mostly via reduced hours support and non-standard only partially covered	No separate scheme – integrated into Kurzarbeit	KfW-Schnellkredit for firms; access to integration & language courses
Ireland	Temporary COVID job retention (via wage subsidy scheme)	Some emergency supports for self-employed	Employment Wage Subsidy Scheme (EWSS) – direct subsidy to companies	Training & reemployment programs in Economic Recovery Plan
Norway	Adjustments to unemployment benefits and layoff rules	General unemployment support and limited targeted inclusion of non-standard	Lønnsstøtteordning – subsidy to rehire employees	Sector-specific reopening grants

Poland	Anti-crisis Shield 1.0/2.0 – employment protection mechanisms	Anti-crisis Shield 1.0 - income support for those on non-standard contracts	Anti-crisis Shield 1.0 – partial wage subsidies for companies	Limited other measures
Spain	ERTE – temporary layoff scheme	Explicit inclusion of self-employed and partial support for non-standard	RDL 25/2020 – direct subsidies to firms /affected sectors	Broader sectoral support

Source: PolicyWatch Eurofound; own elaboration.

Beyond these main pillars, some countries implemented additional measures to support workers often excluded from traditional schemes, particularly the self-employed and those with non-standard contracts. Spain explicitly included self-employed workers in several Royal Decree-Laws, while also providing partial coverage for workers on temporary or part-time contracts. Ireland introduced training and reemployment initiatives as part of its broader recovery strategy. Poland gradually expanded coverage through successive Shields, offering support to micro-enterprises, artists, and workers with civil-law contracts. Germany supplemented its main job retention scheme with liquidity measures and continued to provide access to integration and language courses, though these were not explicitly framed as pandemic measures. Norway focused mainly on temporary adjustments to unemployment benefits and sector-specific reemployment programs.

5. Policy inclusiveness: policies and measures addressed to migrants or migrant-sensitive

Examining how migrants were incorporated into the broader set of labour market policies and measures, our review reveals that the overall coverage of migrant workers was limited, though with marked variation. Table 5 shows what percentage of COVID-19 policies related to the labour market concerned, respectively: migrants directly, migrants indirectly through policies targeting economic sectors or occupations where migrants are overrepresented, as well as non-standard contracts, which often apply to migrant workers. As shown in Table 5 Ireland emerges as the most inclusive case, with the highest share of policies explicitly mentioning migrants, followed by Norway and Spain, while Germany and Poland show lower levels of migrant targeting. This reflects institutional differences: Ireland and Spain developed strategies that combined universal measures with explicit provisions to ensure migrant access, ensuring that eligibility criteria did not depend on nationality or residence status and providing guidance to improve access. In contrast, Germany, Norway, and Poland relied primarily on universal frameworks that were formally open to migrants but lacked specific outreach or adaptation mechanisms (for example, because eligibility requirements for assistance involved submitting applications accessible only

in the host country's language). As shown in Table 5, Ireland reached 15% of policies explicitly targeting migrants, 11% in Norway, 9% in Spain and 6–7% in Germany and Poland. These differences suggest that while migrants were eligible in theory in all countries, in practice their access depended on the design and communication of policies.

Table 5. Policy inclusiveness overview by country

Country	N of measures	Targets migrants	Sectoral coverage	Occupational coverage	Non-standard covered	Non-formal covered
Germany	28	7%	25%	18%	25%	No
Ireland	20	15%	80%	20%	60%	No
Norway	18	11%	39%	6%	22%	No
Poland	16	6%	25%	0%	37%	No
Spain	23	9%	48%	26%	56%	No

Source: own elaboration.

Patterns of coverage across sectors and occupations where migrant workers are overrepresented also vary substantially. Ireland again stands out for its highly targeted approach, with 80% of policies focusing on sectors most affected by the crisis, such as hospitality and retail, where migrants are heavily overrepresented. Spain also shows relatively high levels of targeting (48%), reflecting its focus on tourism and construction, two sectors with a strong concentration of migrant workers. In contrast, Germany and Poland targeted only a quarter of policies to these sectors, while Norway fell in between at 39%. When looking at occupations, the targeting was much more limited. Spain (26%), Ireland (20%) and Germany (18%) were the countries to design measures that explicitly focused on occupational groups with a high share of migrant workers, while Norway (6%) and Poland (0%) paid little to no attention to such distinctions (Table 5).

Differences are particularly striking in how countries addressed different forms of employment. Spain and Ireland were the most proactive, explicitly including non-standard workers (those in part-time employment, working on civil law contracts or solo self-employed) in a large share of their measures (56% and 60%, respectively). Poland provided some targeted support for these workers (37%), while Germany (25%) and Norway (22%) offered only partial coverage. It should be emphasized that policies aimed at supporting non-standard employment should not be equated with indirect support for migrants. Some measures, for example assistance for self-employed workers in artistic professions in Poland, were primarily designed for and benefited native workers. A common finding across all five countries is the complete exclusion of non-formal workers, such as domestic workers or seasonal labourers without formal contracts, with 0% coverage everywhere. This exclusion highlights a structural weakness in labour market protections that transcends welfare state models and policy traditions. The only partial exception is Spain, which introduced a measure aimed at domestic workers. A group where informal employment is highly prevalent. However, eligibility required being registered in the official domestic workers' registry, a condition that effectively excluded many individuals. Despite this limitation, it remains the closest example we identified of a policy seeking to include non-formal workers.

Migrant inclusion varied greatly across the reviewed measures. Ireland and Spain explicitly incorporated migrants into their policy design. Furthermore, in Ireland, this was accompanied by clear guidance to help workers navigate the system, while Spain addressed equal access in legislation for some specific vulnerable groups, particularly in relation to ERTes and subsidies for self-employed workers. In Germany, Norway, and Poland, migrants were formally eligible under universal rules but lacked targeted outreach with some exceptions concerning self-employed and some types of non-standard employment. This distinction is important because migrants are disproportionately concentrated in the sectors and occupations most affected by the pandemic, as well as in non-standard forms of employment, where eligibility gaps are most pronounced.

Access and barriers

Across the five countries, the barriers migrants faced were closely linked to how measures were designed. These insights draw as well on evidence from the PolicyWatch database review. On the one hand, how access to measures was structured in terms of whether workers could apply directly or whether eligibility and applications had to be managed through their employers. This distinction proved crucial in determining how effectively support reached migrants. On the other hand, the information and requirements.

When *job-retention or short-time work schemes* were the main instrument, such as Germany's *Kurzarbeit*, Norway's layoff and benefit adjustments, Poland's Anti-Crisis Shield (1.0) or Spain's *ERTes*, eligibility depended on having a formal employment relationship and previous insurance or contribution records, which excluded those without sufficient insurance history. In these cases, the employer acted as the gatekeeper, applying on behalf of employees and distributing benefits through the payroll system. While administratively efficient, this design systematically disadvantaged migrants working in mini-jobs, part-time roles, temporary agency jobs, or civil-law/atypical contracts, while completely excluding informal workers. If an employer chose not to apply, failed to provide the necessary documentation, or deliberately excluded certain groups of workers (e.g., issues more common in sectors like agriculture, construction, or domestic work) migrants had no option to claim benefits directly. Additionally, procedural hurdles such as online-only applications, long waits for appointments, and processing delays created another layer of the exclusion.

Where *wage-subsidy schemes* were central, such as Ireland's *EWSS*, Norway's *Lønnsstøtteordning*, and some phases of Poland's *Shield* programs, barriers shifted from insurance and contributions history to documentation and payroll attachment. Migrants were at risk of exclusion if they lacked stable payroll ties or if employers could not or would not apply on their behalf. In the case of self-employed workers, grants came with their own gatekeeping mechanisms, such as requirements for tax registration, formal business status, and bank accounts, which excluded many recent arrivals or less-formalized self-employed migrants. Wage subsidy schemes and self-employed supports often allowed for more direct access, though this varied by country. For example, in Ireland, the *EWSS* was administered through employers, but complementary programs for self-employed individuals allowed some workers

to apply independently. In general, direct subsidies for self-employed gave self-employed migrants a direct route to assistance. However, these requirements introduced their own barriers such as migrants without proper tax numbers, banking access, or up-to-date registration which effectively excluded them, despite being formally eligible.

A third set of barriers cut across all policy types. Language and information gaps, particularly when information was provided only through national-language digital portals. For example, in Poland, the deferral of social security contributions for the self-employed, introduced as part of the Anti-Crisis Shield (2.0), required the submission of a relatively complex application. Remote procedures further required access to electronic systems and possession of a digital signature. This left migrants often without access. Ireland stood out for combining wage subsidies with clear guidance and active outreach, including multilingual information campaigns. This helped reduce language and administrative barriers, especially in sectors with high migrant employment, such as hospitality and retail. Other barriers were status and documentation checks, such as the need for valid residency permits, IDs, or work authorizations. Delays in renewals or unclear legal status could invalidate applications.

6. Discussion

This working paper examined how the COVID-19 pandemic affected migrant workers in five European countries: Germany, Ireland, Norway, Poland and Spain, and how labour market policies addressed their vulnerabilities.

The descriptive results highlight the unequal impact of the pandemic on migrants and natives, with clear cross-country variation. Spain experienced severe and persistent effects, as shown by the sharp decline in migrant employment rates and the increase in labour market slack, although both had recovered to pre-pandemic levels by 2022. Germany and Norway also experienced an initial negative impact in 2020, but migrants in these countries recovered quickly, returning to or exceeding pre-pandemic employment levels by 2022. Ireland presented a distinct trajectory, with migrant employment rates remaining relatively stable throughout the pandemic and rising sharply in 2022, surpassing those of natives. Poland stands out as an outlier, with migrants displaying higher employment rate than natives. In line with Mazza et al. (2022), who show that non-EU migrants experienced sharper employment declines and higher risks of termination than natives, our results confirm that relative migrant vulnerability was a constant despite cross-country variation.

These differences reflect both structural labour market characteristics and policy responses. For instance, Germany and Spain exhibited a strong divergence between migrants and natives in terms of labour market slack, underscoring migrants' heightened vulnerability to underemployment and precariousness. In Poland, the decline in actual hours worked was more pronounced for migrants than for natives, indicating that even where job retention schemes helped maintain employment, migrants were more likely to face reductions in working time. Usual hours worked, by contrast, remained relatively stable, suggesting that contractual arrangements were less affected than the actual intensity of work. This pattern implies that

migrants often experienced partial attachment to the labour market during the crisis as also stated by Fasani and Mazza (2020), either through fewer hours or temporary suspensions, rather than outright contract termination.

The policy analysis reveals important differences in how countries addressed (or failed to address) these vulnerabilities. Job retention schemes, wage subsidies and income support measures were central pillars of the pandemic response in all five countries, but their design shaped access for migrants. Universal frameworks, such as Germany's Kurzarbeit, Poland's Anti-Crisis Shield (1.0) or Norway's temporary layoff adjustments, formally included migrants but relied on employers as gatekeepers and required formal contracts and contribution histories. This systematically excluded those in mini-jobs, temporary agency work, or informal employment (i.e., arrangements where migrants are overrepresented) as suggested by Guadagno (2020) and ILO (2021). By contrast, Ireland and Spain combined universal mechanisms with explicit provisions to include migrant workers and non-standard employees. Ireland, in particular, complemented wage subsidies with targeted guidance and multilingual information campaigns, helping reduce barriers linked to language, documentation, and administrative complexity.

Across countries, non-standard workers were only partially included, with Spain and Ireland offering the most extensive coverage. However, a striking and consistent finding across all cases was the complete exclusion of non-formal workers, such as domestic workers or undeclared seasonal labourers. Even Spain's measure for domestic workers required official registration, effectively leaving out many informal workers. This exclusion highlights a structural weakness of European labour market protections: the remaining barriers to access for those in the most precarious situations. As noted by Eichhorst (2022), the design of many job retention schemes left out workers in atypical or informal employment, where migrants are heavily concentrated—a pattern also reflected here. Similarly, Guadagno (2020) and the ILO (2021) underline that migrant women in informal domestic and care work were rarely covered by protective measures.

The lack of explicit targeting of migrants further constrained access, and sectoral and occupational targeting was uneven. This is relevant because, as also raised by Eurofound (2021), sectoral focus indirectly determined migrants' access to support given their concentration in the most affected industries. Ireland's strong focus on hospitality and retail, and Spain's attention to tourism and construction, contrasted with more limited targeting in other countries. This is relevant as sectoral focus indirectly shaped migrant access, given their concentration in contact-intensive industries most affected by lockdowns.

The barriers migrants faced were not only structural but also administrative as also highlighted by other authors (OECD, 2020; Fasani & Mazza, 2023; Mazza et al., 2022). Where benefits were only accessible via employer applications, migrants were dependent on their employers' willingness and ability to navigate the system. In sectors marked by informality, such as agriculture or domestic work, this dependence often resulted in exclusion. Even in countries with theoretically universal systems, practical obstacles (e.g., online-only portals, long waits,

limited language support, and documentation requirements) created a gap between formal eligibility and effective access. In Norway, for example, many migrants working on short-term contracts still only hold a temporary personal identification number (a so-called D-nummber), which prevented them from accessing BankID, the most widely used electronic identification method in Norway. This, in turn, hindered registering in the Labour and Welfare Administration to access online applications for temporary unemployment benefits. This issue was temporary resolved after many months of media campaigns organised by civil society organisations, but it highlighted the oversight in the policies when it comes to migrant inclusion.

Taken together, the findings suggest that while the pandemic responses prevented even more severe employment collapses, they did not fully protect migrant workers. The design of crisis measures assumed in most cases stable, formal employment relationships and access to social security, which systematically disadvantaged migrants concentrated in non-standard and non-formal jobs. The descriptive trends confirm this dynamic: even where employment rates recovered, migrants experienced higher levels of underemployment and reduced working hours, and in countries like Spain, the gap with natives persisted well into the recovery phase.

From a comparative perspective, the case of Ireland demonstrates that more inclusive approaches are possible. By combining universal measures with targeted outreach and accessible implementation mechanisms, it is possible to reduce and mitigate some of the barriers faced by migrants. Conversely, Poland illustrates the limits of fragmented and phased responses, where coverage gaps remained even as migrants maintained high employment rates. Germany and Norway highlight the strengths and weaknesses of universalist measures: while formally open to all, their reliance on formal employment and employer-mediated applications left many migrants effectively excluded.

Policy implications

The analysis underscores several priorities for future crisis. First, extending protections to non-formal and highly precarious workers is essential. This requires not only legal inclusion but also practical mechanisms for direct access, reducing dependency on employer applications. Second, language and information barriers must be addressed proactively through multilingual communication and outreach strategies. Third, sectoral and occupational targeting should be strengthened to ensure that resources reach those most affected by economic shocks, particularly in industries where migrants are heavily concentrated. Finally, better data collection on migrants' labour market experiences is essential. This need to improve the available data is detailed in another working paper of the PATHS2INCLUDE project (Valls et al., 2024).

In conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic acted as a stress test for European labour markets. While emergency measures softened the immediate effects of the pandemic, they also revealed structural inequalities and blind spots in existing systems. Building more inclusive and resilient labour market institutions will require deliberate efforts to close these gaps, ensuring that future crises do not again fall hardest on those already most vulnerable.

Use of artificial intelligence in document analysis

The use of ChatGPT in this working paper demonstrates the potential value of AI as a research assistant, particularly in projects facing constraints in time and human resources. In our case, this approach enabled the detailed review of 105 policy measures, a task that would have been considerably more time-consuming without technological assistance. When appropriately supervised, AI can thus act as a complementary tool that enhances efficiency in qualitative document analysis, supporting researchers in managing extensive datasets or large volumes of textual information.

However, several limitations must be acknowledged. AI systems such as ChatGPT rely on probabilistic language models rather than true understanding, which may lead to occasional misinterpretations or omissions of contextual nuances. The accuracy of its outputs depends heavily on careful prompt design, researcher oversight, and continuous validation of results. Moreover, ethical considerations regarding transparency, accountability, and reproducibility remain central when integrating AI into research workflows. That is, it is essential to make clear how and why AI has been used, researchers must remain responsible for the results and interpretations, and other scholars should be able to understand and, ideally, replicate the process to verify its validity.

In conclusion, while AI cannot replace the critical and interpretive capacities of researchers, it can serve as a valuable tool when its use is well-defined and systematically monitored.

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Appendix 1. ChatGPT instructions

Instructions for ChatGPT

Identifier

Policy name and reference

General policy overview

- What are the eligibility criteria in general?
- Who can apply (target population)?
- What are the benefits and how are they delivered?
- Are the benefits conditional on documentation, contract type, duration, or residency?

Migrant inclusion assessment

For each of the following dimensions, assign one of the categories below (5-point scale) and provide a brief justification:

Valid categories:

- **Explicit** – the group/sector/occupation/... is explicitly mentioned and clearly included.
- **Accessible** – the group/sector/occupation/... is not named but can realistically access the benefit.
- **Unclear** – it's ambiguous whether the group/sector/occupation/... is included or not.
- **Limited** – most of the group/sector/occupation/... is excluded, but some inclusion might be possible.
- **Excluded** – the group/sector/occupation/... is clearly or structurally excluded.

- A. Are migrants/foreigners/non-natives targeted or covered?
- B. Does the policy affect sectors where migrant workers are overrepresented in Spain (specify the relevant country)? (e.g., agriculture, hospitality, domestic work)
- C. Does it affect occupations where migrant workers are overrepresented in Spain (specify the relevant country)? (e.g., cleaners, carers, construction)
- D. Does the policy cover the non-formal sector? (e.g., unregistered or undocumented work)
- E. Does it include non-standard employment? (e.g., part-time, seasonal, temporary work) (it does not refer to informal or non-formal work)

Access

Is this a direct (automatic) benefit or does the person have to apply?

- Direct – automatically granted through payroll or public system
- Apply – requires individual to submit an application or meet criteria

Barriers for non-natives / foreigners / migrants

Indicate any barriers mentioned or implied in the policy:

- Eligibility criteria exclude or disadvantage migrants?
- Special documentation required only from non-natives?
- Are non-natives explicitly excluded?
- Are they implicitly excluded (e.g., via contract type or contribution history)?
- Language or procedural barriers mentioned or likely?

Output format

Structure the analysis using the following format:

1. Identifier
2. Policy name / reference
3. General description (eligibility, target group, benefits)
4. Evaluation by dimension:
 - Migrants targeted: [Category] – Justification
 - Sector affected: [Category] – Justification
 - Occupation affected: [Category] – Justification
 - Non-formal: [Category] – Justification
 - Non-standard: [Category] – Justification
5. Access: [Direct / Apply] - (specify if the individual has to apply or the company; if there is different criteria for employees and self-employed; other)
6. Barriers: [List identified or likely barriers]

Excel output

1. Please add the results of this policy analysis into an Excel file using the following structure:
 - One row per policy
 - Each analytical dimension in a separate column
2. Columns should include:

- Identifier
- Policy name / reference
- Eligibility criteria
- Who can apply
- What are the benefits
- Benefits conditional (e.g., contract type, residency, other)? (Yes/No + explanation)
- Migrants targeted – Category
- Migrants targeted – Justification
- Migrants targeted – Literal quote (add section + page)
- Sectors affected – Category
- Sectors affected – Justification
- Sectors affected – Literal quote (add section + page)
- Occupations affected – Category
- Occupations affected – Justification
- Occupations affected – Literal quote (add section + page)
- Non-formal sector – Category
- Non-formal – Justification
- Non-formal – Literal quote (add section + page)
- Non-standard employment – Category
- Non-standard – Justification
- Non-standard – Literal quote (add section + page)
- Access modality
- Access modality – Literal quote (add section + page)
- Barriers for migrants
- Barriers for migrants – Literal quote (add section + page)

Important:

- If this is the first policy being analysed, create a new Excel file.
- If this is not the first policy, add a new row to the existing Excel file used for policy tracking.

Appendix 2. Exclusion criteria

1. Included and excluded categories and sub-categories / depend on the specific measure

Employment protection and retention

- Income support for people in employment (INCLUDED)
- Other (INCLUDED)
- Wage flexibility (INCLUDED)
- Working time flexibility (INCLUDED)

Ensuring business continuity and support for essential services

- Smoothing frictions or reallocation of workers (INCLUDED)
- Change of work arrangements (working time, rota schemes) (INCLUDED)
- Remuneration and rewards for workers in essential services (INCLUDED)
- Mobilisation of a larger workforce (EXCLUDED)

Income protection beyond short-time work

- Income support for unemployed (INCLUDED)
- Support for parents and carers (financial or in kind) (INCLUDED)
- Extensions of income support to workers not covered by any kind of protection schemes (INCLUDED)
- Paid sick leave – self-employed and small businesses (INCLUDED)

Measures to prevent social hardship

- Protection of vulnerable groups (beyond employment support) (EXCLUDED)
- Keeping or obtaining a safe home (EXCLUDED)
- Access to childcare and education
- Access to healthcare (Ukrainian) (EXCLUDED)
- Other humanitarian measures (EXCLUDED)
- Preventing over-indebtedness (EXCLUDED)

- Provision of services in kind (e.g. food vouchers) (EXCLUDED)

Promoting the economic, labour market and social recovery

- Flexibilisation and security (INCLUDED)
- Active labour market policies (enhancing employability, training, subsidised job creation, etc.) (INCLUDED)
- Support for spending, stimulus packages (EXCLUDED)
- Measures to support a gradual relaunch of work (INCLUDED)
- Other (INCLUDED)

Protection of workers, adaptation of workplace

- Teleworking arrangements, remote working (INCLUDED)
- Changes of working hours or work arrangements (INCLUDED)
- Occupational health and safety (EXCLUDED)
- Changes in work organization (INCLUDED)
- Changes of management approach (EXCLUDED)
- Well-being of workers (INCLUDED)

Reorientation of business activities

- Transfer or redeployment of workers (EXCLUDED)
- Change of production/innovation (EXCLUDED)
- Matching/networking (EXCLUDED)
- Creation of platforms for businesses aimed at customer (EXCLUDED)

Responses to inflation

- Support for fuel expenses (EXCLUDED)
- Increasing income in general (INCLUDED)
- Support for energy bills (EXCLUDED)
- Support for other basic items (e.g., food, housing, public transport, medicines) (EXCLUDED)

Supporting businesses to stay afloat

- Direct subsidies (full or partial) (INCLUDED)
- Access to finance (EXCLUDED)
- Deferral of payments or liabilities (INCLUDED)

- Foreign trade related measures (EXCLUDED)
- Rescue procedures in case of insolvency or adaptation of insolvency regulation (INCLUDED)
- Other (INCLUDED)

2. According to the pre-selected cases, the following exclusion criteria were applied

Exclusion criteria – second phase

Exclude policies from the analysis in the following cases:

- Policies that were created or implemented outside the COVID-19 period, specifically those not introduced between 2020 and 2022.
- Policies that are not related to the COVID-19 crisis, such as those implemented in response to other events (e.g., the war in Ukraine).
- Measures that are not related to the labour market (e.g., policies focused solely on public health or poverty).
- Business-focused measures that have no direct or indirect impact on workers.

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